

STEEL RIBBON REINFORCED EPOXY PIPE

J. Rexer*, E. Anderson*, G. Fourty*,
C. Bournazel**, J. Corteville**

Abstract

Two-dimensional reinforcement, by ribbons or flakes, is especially well-suited for biaxially stressed structures. Steel ribbon-reinforced pipes have been developed for application as risers for off-shore oil platforms. Fabrication is by helical winding of 10 to 25 layers (0.25 to 0.60 volume fraction) of high strength steel ribbon (210 kg/mm²) in an epoxy matrix. Tensile strength in the circumferential direction is determined by the steel strength and content, and furthermore in the axial direction by the "critical stress transfer width" (similar to the critical length in discontinuous fibre composites) and by the ribbon arrangement.

Axial strengths are typically between 50 and 75% of the circumferential. With a steel width to thickness ratio of 400 the pipes have identical elastic moduli in both principle directions. The torsion modulus shows no anisotropy. Strength characteristics measured on 80 mm diameter pipes are compared with results on test coupons. Burst, collapse and compressive strengths are close to theoretical and, as with alternating fatigue, final failure coincides with failure of the steel ribbons. Given, in addition, other interesting properties (high resistance to chemical agents, low radial thermal conductivity) it is possible to design the composite structure to satisfy the wide variety of constraints that are met in off-shore, pressure pipelines, etc.

* Battelle-Geneva, Research Institute, 7, route de Drize, CH-1227 Carouge-GE

** Institut français du Pétrole, 1-4, av. Bois Préau, F-92502 Reuil-Malmaison

INTRODUCTION

The results presented here were obtained in a research program aimed at the development of light-weight, high-strength pipes for applications in off-shore oil production. Composite materials are obvious candidates for such applications but conventional filament reinforced types have several drawbacks which had to be overcome. For example, in the case of glass filament reinforced plastics:

- the modulus is relatively low
- the very nature of the fibrous reinforcement implies that either complicated filament winding procedures, or helical windings and axial lay-up are required to obtain a pipe reinforced in both the circumferential and axial directions; such fabrication is complex
- the fine bundles of filaments are difficult to impregnate, leaving air bubbles and resin-free zones. These zones, allied to the cross-ply nature of the structure lead to delamination and weeping at relatively low stresses.

The replacement of glass filaments by steel wires¹⁾ of greater diameter and higher modulus leads to improvement in some of the above characteristics, but complex winding or lay-up techniques are still required to obtain optimum pipe reinforcement.

Two-dimensional reinforcement of sheet materials can be obtained by the incorporation of high strength ribbons into a metallic²⁻⁵⁾ or a plastic matrix. Ribbons and other elongated cross section elements have been used for improving the rigidity of flexible, elastomeric matrix hose pipes. The results of recent studies on the reinforcement of sheets of other polymer matrices-polycarbonate by steel discs⁶⁾ and polyethylene by steel ribbons⁷⁾ - confirm the obtention of two-dimensional reinforcement. However, no attempt has yet been made to produce high strength epoxy resin reinforced pipes by such an approach.

THEORY OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL REINFORCEMENT

The helical winding in a resin matrix of steel ribbon leads to a tubular structure reinforced continuously in the circumferential direction and discontinuously in the axial direction. Thus, the rules of continuous and discontinuous filament reinforcement respectively can be applied. Figure 1 shows a typical pipe and the axial cross section obtained.

In the text which follows the terms circumferential and axial for the properties of the pipes correspond respectively to the continuous ribbon direction and the direction transverse to the ribbons in the composite material itself. In actual fact the ribbons are

wound in the pipe at a slight angle to 90° so that there is not exact correspondence. The effect on the mechanical properties, however, is minimal.

Elastic modulus

The circumferential elastic modulus, E_c of the pipe is given by the well-known rule of mixtures

$$E_c = \sum E_i V_i \quad (1)$$

where E_i and V_i are respectively the elastic modulus and volume fraction of the matrix and reinforcement.

In the axial pipe direction this relation is approximately valid for ratios of ribbon width to thickness greater than a critical value which depends on the modulus ratio of the constituents, and is around 400 in the present case⁸).

Mechanical strength

The circumferential strength, σ_c of the pipe is given by the relation

$$\sigma_c = \sum \sigma_i V_i \quad (2)$$

where σ_i is respectively the strength of the steel and the stress on the matrix at fracture of the composite.

The reinforcement in the axial direction is discontinuous and the ratio of ribbon width to the thickness plays an important role in determining the strength. In order to have an efficient load transfer from the matrix to the ribbons, the following critical aspect ratio relation must be obeyed:

$$\frac{W}{t} > \frac{\sigma_r}{\tau} \quad (3)$$

where W and t are respectively the ribbon width and thickness, σ_r the steel fracture strength and τ the shear strength of the matrix or the matrix/ribbon interface, whichever is the weakest.

The composite structure obtained with ribbons differs from the usual discontinuous fibre reinforcement by its regular nature which leads to regions of relative weakness, as can be seen in Figure 1 and in Figure 2 for a ribbon arrangement with an overlap length, $l_o = W/2$. In this case a maximum of 50% of the ribbons can be stressed to rupture, thus giving an axial pipe strength about half that in the circumferential direction. Such a reinforcement

corresponds ideally to the stresses developed in a pipe under the influence of only an internal pressure. However, for applications where supplementary stresses such as bending or traction are imposed, the axial strength of the pipe can be increased by designing with other ribbon arrangements such that the overlap length, $\ell_o < W/2$ (while still meeting the critical aspect ratio criterion(3)).

The general equation for the transverse strength of ribbon composites is (see Figure 2):

$$\sigma_{trans.} = \sigma'_m (1-f_{br}) V_r + \sigma_r f_{br} V_r + \sigma_r \frac{\ell_o^*}{W_c} (1-f_{br}) V_r \quad (4)$$

where W_c is the critical ribbon width given by equation (3) and ℓ_o^* is as defined in Fig. 2 and is due to the small irregularities in ribbon lay-up introduced during the winding process. The third factor on the right hand side of equation (4) represents a pull-out contribution to the overall strength which is rather low (< 5%) provided the adhesion bond between the ribbon and the matrix is good.

The factor f_{br} indicate the maximum fraction of ribbons that can be stressed to rupture by a transverse loading of the specimen and depends on the type of ribbon arrangement. Provided that the critical aspect ratio is obeyed, ie. $W_c/2 < \ell_o$, the factor f_{br} will equal $(n-1)/n$ for an overlap length $\ell_o = W/n$ (n is a whole number). In the case of $n = 2$, f_{br} will be 0.5 and, neglecting the third factor, equation (4) reduces to

$$\sigma_{trans.} = \sigma'_m (1-0.5V_r) + 0.5 V_r \sigma_r \quad (5)$$

If $W_c/2 > \ell_o$, all the ribbons will be pulled out ($f_{br} = 0$) and the transverse rupture strength of the composite is given by the rupture strength of the matrix, σ'_m and a pull-out term analogous to the third factor of equation (4):

$$\sigma_{trans.} = \sigma'_m + \sigma_r V_r \frac{\ell_o}{W_c} f_{po} \quad (6)$$

The factor f_{po} now indicates the fraction of pulled-out ribbons and is given by the same relation as previously for the factor f_{br} :

$$f_{po} = \frac{n-1}{n} \quad \text{for} \quad \ell_o = \frac{W}{n}$$

If the adhesion strength, τ becomes zero, $W_c \rightarrow \infty$ and all the transverse rupture strength will be given by the rupture strength of the resin matrix.

MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

The basic constituents finally used for the pipe fabrication were examined during a step-wise screening program which resulted in the following choice:

Steel ribbons: cold-rolled carbon steel of 180-210 da N/mm² tensile strength and 21,500 da N/mm² elastic modulus; 0.1 mm thick ribbons either 20 or 40 mm wide. The surface treatment for optimum adhesion to the matrix resin consisted essentially of degreasing followed by an acid attack.

Resin: the mechanical and chemical demands on the resin (e.g. good adhesion to steel at 100°C, resistance at 100°C to alkaline mud, petrol and gas) quickly limited the choice to epoxies. The final epoxy resin employed presented excellent chemical properties and was of the following composition:

100 parts: glycidylether type epoxy resin + 27 parts
diaminodiphenyl methane + 25 parts: grade 7 asbestos

with the following properties:

elastic modulus	=	300	da N/mm ²
tensile strength	=	5.5	"
compressive strength	=	12	"
flexural strength	=	10	"

The shear strength of the resin/steel ribbon bond was measured in a three-ribbon lap shear test; at room temperature $\tau = 3.5$ daN/mm² and at 100°C $\tau = 2.7$ daN/mm² for an overlap length of 5mm.

The machine used for the fabrication of 80 mm diameter - 1 metre long pipes is shown in Fig. 3. The resin mixture was prepared just before fabrication and applied to one side of the steel ribbon being wound on a steel mandrel. Pipes with 10, 15, 20 and 25 layers of steel ribbon, steel volume fractions of 0.25 to 0.60 and ribbon overlaps, l_0 of W/2 and W/4 were prepared. Curing at 120-140°C was followed by removal from the mandrel. This operation was facilitated by deposition of a hardened silicone varnish layer on the slightly conical, highly polished mandrel.

The final pipe thickness varied from 2 to 5 mm depending on steel content and number of layers.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The various mechanical characteristics of the composite material were determined by tests on specimens cut out of the pipes and by tests on the pipes themselves.

Transverse tensile specimens

The specimens were carefully machined in the axial direction of the composite pipes, being 115 mm in total length with a reduced mid-section of 60 mm by 10 mm wide. Special grip pieces were employed which fitted exactly the specimen curvature. Both elastic modulus, with the aid of an extensometer, and tensile strength were determined with this test, and the results are presented in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively.

Pipe tensile and burst

The various composite pipes of about 1m length were fitted with specially adapted end junctions, as seen in Fig. 7, in order to carry out the tensile and burst tests. Using the same epoxy resin as the matrix no leakage or failure was observed up to tensile forces of 27 tons.

In the tensile test the axial elastic modulus and strength were measured, while the burst test under internal hydrostatic pressure without end effects gave a value of the circumferential rupture strength. These values are again plotted in Figs. 4 and 5.

Collapse

The composite pipe specimens were tested under conditions of external hydrostatic pressure up to final collapse. In the case of the thin pipes of about 2 mm wall thickness the final collapse pressure corresponded to elastic buckling in the circumferential direction, as predicted by the classical Euler formula. The elastic moduli calculated are presented in Fig. 4.

Compression

The pipe specimens shown in Fig. 8 were tested to failure in compression allowing values of the axial elastic modulus and compression strength to be obtained. The 100 mm long specimens were machined with perfectly parallel ends and adhesive bonded into solid supports. The modulus values are plotted in Fig. 4 and the compressive strength in Fig. 9.

Fatigue

The fatigue tests were carried out under conditions of alternating stress about a mean imposed bend stress on the 1 metre long

pipes fitted with steel rings at the ends and in the centre. These rings, respectively 50 and 75 mm long and 2 mm thick were adhesive bonded to the pipe and their function was to enable the cyclic bending forces to be applied without the risk of damaging the composite pipes at the region of force application.

The cycles were always carried out about the mean imposed initial bend stress with no inversion about zero. The results are presented in Fig. 10 in the form of a Goodman diagram.

Torsion

Torsion tests were performed on 1 metre long composite pipe samples fitted with special end junctions. The measured values of the shear modulus, G are given in Fig. 4. Shorter pipe lengths (30 cm), intended for strength measurements, resisted up to moments of 600 kp.m., at which point the adhesive bonded end junction failed.

DISCUSSION

Elastic modulus

The experimental values of Young's modulus, E are compared in Fig. 4 with the theoretical straight lines calculated from the rule of mixtures equation (1). The agreement with theory is good for pipes containing 40 mm wide ribbons (aspect ratio 400) and as predicted by theory, the circumferential (continuous) and the axial (transverse) moduli are practically identical.

The transverse moduli of the tensile specimens cut out of the composite pipes correspond to 92 and 96% of the expected moduli of discontinuous ribbon composites with ribbons of 20 and 40 mm respectively. In the former case the relatively low value can be explained by the fact that the aspect ratio is lower than that demanded by theory in order to have isotropic elastic properties in a ribbon composite ⁸⁾.

The shear modulus, G is identical in both senses of torsion showing that no complicated ribbon cross-winding is required to obtain isotropic torsion properties. This result can be explained by the excellent bond between the resin and the steel ribbons.

The values of Poisson's ratio calculated from the measured shear moduli and the theoretical Young's modulus (Fig. 4) are 0,33 and 0,36, which correspond well with the Poisson's ratios calculated by the mixture rule.

Tensile strength

The values measured on tensile specimens and pipes are compared with the theoretical lines in Fig. 5. The circumferential strength of a pipe tested without end effects gives a result close to the theoretical value calculated by relation (2) for continuous ribbon composites. The axial pipe and transverse composite specimen strengths with $\ell_o = W/2 > \ell_c$ fit very well with theory for two types of resin:

- A: that finally chosen for the application and described previously, and
- B: another monocomponent epoxy resin, which exhibited a high bond strength to steel ($\tau = 2.8 \text{ daN/mm}^2$ for an overlap length of 5mm.)

Composites with this latter resin B exhibited strengths for an overlap, $\ell_o = W/4 = 5 \text{ mm}$ which were similar to the strengths obtained with $\ell_o = W/2 = 10 \text{ mm}$. Thus, the critical overlap width $W_c/2 < 5 \text{ mm}$. Resin A, on the other hand gave lower rupture strengths with $\ell_o = 5 \text{ mm}$ due to the lower value of interfacial shear strength.

Samples cut from pipes containing alternate cross-wound ribbon layers exhibited tensile strengths close to those for simple helical wound pipes. This, together with the observation on the isotropy of the shear modulus, shows that, given a high steel/resin interfacial bond strength, cross winding is not necessary to obtain isotropic pipe properties.

The photomicrograph in Fig. 6 of the side view of the fracture surface of a transverse composite specimen shows that fracture took place approximately normal to the tensile axis with only a limited delamination of steel ribbons from the matrix.

It can be seen that half of the ribbons have failed in shear in agreement with the actual ribbon arrangement ($\ell_o = W/2$).

The plastic elongation to rupture of the composites, specimens or pipes, is in the region of 0.5 to 0.6 % which correspond to the failure strain of the steel ribbons.

Compressive strength

Fig. 9 presents the results obtained in compression tests on samples of the type shown in Fig. 8. It is not possible to explain the results on the basis neither of an elastic matrix/elastic fiber⁹⁾ nor of a plastic matrix/elastic fiber composite¹⁰⁾. However, in agreement with Moncunill et al.¹¹⁾ the compressive strength was found to be an approximately linear function of the volume, and related to the yield strength of the steel ribbons and the matrix respectively.

The fact that the failure surface on the composite pipes follows the helical path of the ribbons at the level of the junctions between successive turns suggests that the failure is associated with an instability in the region of the ribbon junctions. During straining those regions on ribbons at the level of junctions between ribbons in the adjacent layers are exposed to the highest stresses due to stress concentration effects. Thus, it is probable that the ribbons yield initially in these regions and, since they are also less well radially supported, a buckle will develop in the ribbon. This in turn results in a rapid transfer of stress to the matrix which fails.

Fatigue resistance

The results of the fatigue tests can be represented on a Goodman diagram as illustrated in Fig. 10. The stress values, $\sigma_{\text{mean}} \pm \sigma_{\text{alt}}$ between which the pipes were cycled were chosen on the basis of the pipe strengths, σ_{trans} measured on tensile specimens cut out of the pipe extremities. Thus, the absolute values might vary from test to test but the comparative values have been plotted in Fig. 10. The necessity, for experimental reasons, to carry out the tests on pipes with adhesive bonded steel rings resulted always in fatigue failures on the compression side of the pipe in the region of the centre ring. In all the tests no reduction in the modulus was observed up to the final rupture of the pipe.

On a microscopic scale the fracture consists of broken ribbons with some ribbon/matrix delamination produced either before or by the ribbon fracture. The fatigue limit (50 % rupture) of the steel ribbons at 2×10^6 cycles is 50 ± 50 daN/mm² i.e.

$$\frac{2\sigma}{9} r + \frac{2\sigma}{9} r$$

Thus, if the steel controls the fatigue limit of the composite pipes the same relation should hold-which is approximately true as shown in Fig. 10. The same correlation between composite and steel fatigue life was found previously for aluminium - steel ribbon composites³).

The effect of fatigue cycling on the pipe strength was measured in bending on a pipe which had undergone 2×10^6 cycles at stresses of

$$\frac{\sigma_{\text{trans.}}}{3} + \frac{\sigma_{\text{trans.}}}{8}$$

The elastic modulus was 7 400 daN/mm² compared with 8 400 daN/mm² theoretical, i.e. a reduction of about 12% which could indicate that a slight delamination of the composite had taken place during fatigue.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The simple helical winding of high strength steel ribbons in an epoxy matrix produces composite pipes with high specific strength.
2. The mechanical characteristics of the composite materials were determined on specimens cut out of the pipes and on the 1 metre long pipes themselves.
3. The elastic behaviour of the composite pipe is isotropic, with respect to both Young's modulus and the shear modulus.
4. The strength in the circumferential pipe direction is governed by the laws of continuous filament reinforcement.
5. In the axial pipe direction the strength is given by laws similar to those governing reinforcement by discontinuous fibres, provided that the overlap between ribbons in adjacent layers is greater than a critical value determined principally by the interfacial shear strength.
6. The compression strength of the pipe in the axial direction is controlled by the yielding of the ribbons at the level of the junctions between ribbons in the adjacent layers.
7. The axial fatigue strength, measured on the pipes in alternating bend about a superimposed mean stress is determined by the fatigue strength of the steel ribbons.

OUTLOOK

The good correlation with theory allows extrapolation, with some degree of confidence, to larger pipe dimensions, either in the case of pipelines or containers. The material combines an excellent corrosion resistance with the strength of a high quality steel but for only half the density. The very nature of the composite structure allows great flexibility in the optimisation of, for example, the burst and collapse strengths for off-shore applications¹²).

The real potential of the material may, however, lie in the continuous, on-site fabrication of high pressure pipelines. The advantages of corrosion resistance, high specific strength, reduced welding, high fracture resistance, etc. would lead to pipelines highly competitive, technically and economically with actual steel lines both on land and off-shore.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work presented here was supported at Battelle-Geneva by the Institut français du Pétrole, whose kind permission to publish is acknowledged. The authors would also like to thank MM. Delacour, Huvey and Peinado, Institut français du Pétrole and MM. Lux and Carrière, Battelle-Geneva for their help and encouragement during this project, and MM. Henrioux and Reymond, Battelle-Geneva for their assistance in the pipe fabrication and testing.

REFERENCES

1. F.F. Jaray, Ind. and Eng. Chem., 59(10), 1967, 83.
2. E. Anderson, B. Lux, C. Crussard, Revue de Métallurgie 2 (1972) 165
3. E. Anderson, J. Materials Science 8 (1973) 676
4. E. Anderson, R. Bode, in Failure Modes in Composites, Proc. Symp. Spons. Met. Soc. AIME, Boston (May 1972) 289.
5. J. Rexer, E. Anderson, to appear in Z. Aluminium
6. B. Glavinchevski, M. Piggot, J. Materials Science 8 (1973) 1373.
7. T. B. Lewis, 25th Annual Techn. Conference (1970) Reinforced Plastics/Composites Division, Sect. 8-D
8. J.C. Halpin and R.L. Thomas, J. Comp. Mat. 2, (4), (1968) 488.
9. B.W. Rosen, Fibre Composite Materials, Am. Soc. Metals, (1965) p.37.
10. N.F. Dow, B.W. Rosen and Z. Hashin, NASA-CR-492, June 1966.
11. E. Moncunill de Ferran and B. Harris, J. Composite Materials 4 (1970) 62.
12. J. Corteville, M. Peinado, C. Bournazel, M. Huvey, J. Rexer, G. Fourty, E. Anderson, Revue de l'Institut français du Pétrole, Dez. 1974.

Figure 1: Epoxy-steel ribbon pipe with inset axial section (x 20) showing steel ribbon arrangement

$$\sigma_{\text{transv.}} = \underbrace{\sigma_m^i (1 - f_{br} V_r)}_{\text{matrice contribution}} + \underbrace{\sigma_r f_{br} V_r}_{\text{broken ribbons}} + \underbrace{\sigma_r \frac{l^*}{W_c} (1 - f_{br}) V_r}_{\text{pulled out contribution}}$$

Figure 2: Transverse rupture strength of ribbon reinforced composites.

Figure 5: Tensile strength of steel ribbon-reinforced epoxy resin composites

tensile specimens

pipes

$l_0 = 10$ mm

$l_0 = 5$ mm

cross-ply

resin A Δ
resin B \square

Δ
 \square

Δ
 \square

\boxtimes

\circ

Figure 6: Cross-section of rupture surface of epoxy-steel ribbon composite tensile specimen showing mixture of fractured and pulled-out ribbons (x 50)

Burst

collapse

flexure

Figure 7: Composite pipes ruptured under various stress conditions.

Figure 8: Composite pipe specimens (100 mm long x 80 mm diameter) ruptured in axial compression.

Figure 9: Compressive strength of steel ribbon reinforced epoxy pipes. $\sigma_{v,r}$ and $G_{y,m}$ are yield strength of ribbons and matrix respectively.

Figure 10: Goodman diagram of the fatigue behaviour of steel ribbon reinforced epoxy pipes.

- Failure in $\sim 5 \times 10^4$ cycles
- No failure in 2×10^6 cycles.